

Cost-Effectiveness evaluation of Ambulatory and Hospital Care for MDR-TB Treatment in Pakistan: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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ABSTRACT: The rank of Pakistan is fourth in the high multidrug resistance tuberculosis (MDR-TB) burden countries. To combat the disease in a resource-scarce setting, it is important to explore treatment regimens that are safe, efficient, and cost-effective. A decision tree model is employed for cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) of treatment arms, quantifying their value through incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICER). In 2012-2017, randomized control trials were conducted in Lahore, Murree, and Karachi comparing two MDR-TB treatment care arms by collecting the data of 342 newly diagnosed patients. The results show that continuous dominance is not depicted by either arm while both demonstrated their value in reducing the disease burden for MDR-TB patients in Pakistan. Hence both approaches can be simultaneously considered viable strategies for treatment.

Keywords: Cost-effectiveness, DALYs, Ambulatory care, Hospital Care, MDR-TB, Pakistan

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1. Introduction

Pakistan ranks fifth among the high Tuberculosis (TB) burden countries and fourth for Multi-drug Resistance Tuberculosis (MDR-TB) in the world (WHO, 2020). Treatment of MDR-TB is challenging for public health systems not only in Pakistan but globally as second-line TB drugs are expensive and less effective (Ramachandra and Swaminathan, 2015). Hence in the resource-scarce setting, the frameworks ruling the development expenditure and resource allocation for sound policy interventions play an important role in deciding the relative effectiveness and costs of competing intervention strategies (Hutubessy et al., 2003; Ahmed et al 2024; Aslam et al 2024; Ashraf and Shabbir 2019; Ehsan et al 2023; Shabbir et al 2020). The economic evaluation of the treatment strategies is vital to understand and expand the range of TB treatment options available in the health systems to eliminate TB by 2035 as envisioned by the World Health Organization (WHO) and Sustainable Development Goals. Pakistan has to take sound steps to achieve this

target as each year almost 510,000 new TB cases are reported with 15,000 cases for MDR-TB patients (WHO, 2022).

The incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)- a metric comparing the additional cost per unit of health benefit of the two treatment arms (AC and HC) would be calculated to determine which treatment arm is more viable for eradicating the MDR-TB in Pakistan. By analyzing disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) averted and social costs in both arms, using the sample of 342 MDR-TB patients from 2012 to 2017 in Lahore, Karachi, and Murree, we aim to draw evidence-based policy implications on which treatment approach offers a greater benefit for every dollar spent, ultimately informing better resource allocation strategies for MDR-TB program in Pakistan.

Incremental cost, measured in monetary units, reflects the difference in social cost combining the medical and non-medical expenditures for program and patient expenditures between the two treatment arms (Bhatti et al 2023; Hayat et al 2022; Liu et al 2023). Incremental effectiveness, on the other hand, is non-monetary and calculated as the difference in disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) averted. DALYs represent the years of healthy life lost due to disease, with one DALY equating to one lost year of perfect health hence reduction in DALYs is considered as a benefit (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2013; Shabbir 2016; Fahamsyah et al 2023;). DALYs are also economically valued using the country's GDP per capita per year, making them an efficient tool for cost-effectiveness analyses. A critical threshold used in global health studies to assess cost-effectiveness is ICER, which compares the additional cost per DALY averted. It is calculated by dividing the difference in cost between two strategies by the difference in their effectiveness. An ICER less than one or three times the annual GDP per capita suggests a cost-effective strategy, reflecting the trade-off between resource value and health gains (Marseille et al., 2015, Shabbir et al 2020; Robinson et al., 2016 and Daroudi et al., 2021). This framework will help us to compare and contrast alternative treatment options, guiding informed resource allocation decisions for Pakistan's MDR-TB program. The secondary objectives of the study encompass the deep dive into the cost burden on the patients, and the evaluation of cost per DALY averted for both arms.

The structure of the study encompasses the literature review in Section 2, the methodology is explained in Section 3, the results in Section 4 followed by a conclusion and recommendation in Section 5.

2. Literature Review

Some studies have suggested that if managed properly, AC can achieve comparable cure rates as that of traditional HC programs. For instance, studies in Thailand (Kamolratanakul et al., 1999), Tanzania (Lwilla et al., 2003), Zambia (Miti, 2003), Kenya (Kangangi et al., 2003), and India (Singh et al., 2004) demonstrate non-significant differences in clinical outcomes between hospital and ambulatory care for MDR-TB treatment. Zweifel et al. (2009) argue that cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) can offer a robust framework for healthcare decision-making, especially when considering both health outcomes and resource limitations. By incorporating social perspectives, CEA can inform government officials about the most efficient allocation of scarce resources within the

healthcare system, maximizing health benefits for the population (Sikandar et al 2023; Liang et al 2023; Shabbir 2016; Rawoof et al 2023; Nawaz et al 2022). CEA can guide healthcare providers and policymakers in choosing the most cost-effective interventions and service delivery models given the resource constraint. In literature, while the effectiveness of various treatment regimens for MDR-TB has been extensively studied, comparatively little research has explored their cost-effectiveness. This gap presents an obstacle in optimizing resource allocation and achieving affordable MDR-TB control strategies.

The success of ambulatory care for MDR-TB treatment relies not only on its clinical feasibility but also on sound community support systems (WHO, 2003). Kangovi et al. (2009) highlight the essential role of community-based workers in MDR-TB treatment through a meta-analysis of treatment outcomes. The findings suggest that providing financial or other tangible rewards to community workers in developing countries can enhance their commitment that will increase the program effectiveness as well. Moreover, healthcare workers adopting empathetic and supportive behaviour can create a comfortable environment for the patients encouraging them to complete their treatment.

Various types of costs are associated with the treatment of Tuberculosis (TB) for example a systematic analysis by Barter et al. (2012) investigated 30 articles for the Sub-Saharan region to explore the cost of TB treatment in the region. Medication, hospitalization, transportation, and caregiving in the private sector were identified as the major cost drivers. The financial burden varied among the patients ranging from a small proportion to 10 times their average income indicating a need of immediate and sound policy interventions.

Fitzpatrick and Floyd (2012) conducted a comprehensive review of literature across 14 WHO sub-regions, concluding that ambulatory care offered a lower cost per DALY averted compared to hospital care for MDR-TB treatment. This suggests that outpatient management can achieve comparable health outcomes economically. While hospital care is a common trend, research directs towards the potential benefits of shifting towards community-based models in South Asia. Khan et al. (2002) highlighted the challenges faced by Pakistani patients due to daily hospital visits in the initial treatment phase. Loss of working hours and associated financial burdens can impact adherence and overall treatment success. Community-based ambulatory care could potentially reduce these hurdles. Several studies (John et al 2018; Sikandar et al 2023; Shabbir 2018; Nawaz et al 2022; Rehman et al 2023; Qing et al 2024; and Gomez et al 2016) found evidence of cost savings associated with ambulatory care in India and Bangladesh, respectively. This reinforces the economic advantages of shifting away from hospital care treatment.

Moreover, a few critical aspects identified in the literature about the CEA are difficulty in data availability especially the direct and indirect cost of treatment, unclear assumptions used by the researchers, lack of sensitivity analysis to test the robustness of results and detailed calculations (Fox-Rushby and Hanson, 2001; Shabbir et al 2023; Tabasam et al 2023; Wang et al 2023; Xue et al 2024; Yan et al 2024; & WHO, 2009). In this research, we have tried to bridge these gaps not only by contributing to the global understanding of cost-effectiveness for MDR-TB treatment arms but also by outlining data-

driven evidence for Pakistan to support its healthcare policy decisions to attain the goal of TB free environment.

3. Methodology

To guide effective health interventions for MDR-TB, this study employs cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA). CEA evaluates the trade-off between cost (monetary units) and health benefits (DALYs averted) for two treatment arms. This analysis helps decision-makers understand how much society is willing to invest in achieving improved health outcomes for patients with MDR-TB.

3.1. Effectiveness measure of health intervention strategies

This study uses disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) to compare the effectiveness of two treatments arms for MDR-TB: hospital care and ambulatory care. DALYs consider both the years of life lost due to premature death (YLLs) and the years lived with disability due to illness (YLDs). This comprehensive measure provides a clearer picture of the overall burden of MDR-TB and the potential impact of each treatment option. i.e. "One DALY is thus one lost year of healthy life" as it measures the loss of life caused by the disease and reduction in DALYs is considered a benefit (Murray et al., 1994, Zhang et al 2023; Shabbir and Wisdom 2020; IHME,2010 and Drent, 2011). Following Fox-Rushby and Hanson (2001), the incremental effectiveness is taken as a difference in DALYs the HC and AC.

Moreover, standard life expectancy might not capture socio-economic disparities. Instead, this study uses gender-based local life expectancy for Pakistan, as suggested by Murray (1996). The discount rates reflect the present societal value of future health gains. This analysis considers three discount rates i.e. zero giving equal weight to present and future value, 3% risk-free rate taken equivalent to the U.S treasury real interest rate and 5.96% average as the real interest rate from 2011-2017 in Pakistan. (Economic Survey of Pakistan, 2018).

The years of life lived with disability (YLD) and the years of life lost (YLL) are calculated by using Equations 2.1 and 2.2 respectively as proposed by Fox-Rushby and Hanson (2001).

$$YLD_i(r, M, \alpha) = D \left[\frac{MZe^{rao}}{(r + \alpha)^2} \{ e^{-(r+\alpha)(Ld+ao)} [-(r + \alpha)(Ld + ao) - 1] - e^{-(r+\alpha)ao} [-(r + \alpha)ao - 1] \} + \frac{1 - M}{r} (1 - e^{-rLd}) \right] \quad 1$$

$$YLL_i(r, M, \alpha) = \frac{MZe^{rad}}{(r + \alpha)^2} \{ e^{-(r+\alpha)(Le+ad)} [-(r + \alpha)(Le + ad) - 1] - e^{-(r+\alpha)ad} [-(r + \alpha)ad - 1] \} + \frac{1 - M}{r} (1 - e^{-rLe}) \quad 2$$

Here,

M = age weighting modulation factor, 0 for uniform weights and 1 for non-uniform weights

$Z = 0.1658$ = Age weighing adjustment constant to normalize the impact of non-uniform age weights so they do not disturb the total number of DALYs

Le = Loss function of years of life loss estimated by gender-based local life expectation at age ad

ad = age of death

r = discount rate

$\alpha = 0.04$ = age weighting constant

ao = age of onset of disability

Ld = duration of disability

D = disability weight

i = i th number of patient

YLD = years of life lived with disability

YLL = years of life lost

YLL calculation employs a two-stage approach (Fox-Rushby and Hanson, 2001). In the first step, Equation 2 estimates YLL directly from the age of death. This initial value reflects immediate impact of the disease on lifespan. Then in the next step, it is translated to the total life years lost from death (Equation 2) to the expected life lost from disability onset, making it compatible for calculating the overall years of life lost due to premature death i.e. YLL.

Equation 3 converts the YLL based on age of death (YLL_i at age ad), into YLL at the onset of disability ($YLL_i(r, M, \alpha)$). This is achieved by discounting the duration of disease ($ad - \text{onset age}$) with a rate r and applying a scaling factor M and exponent α from Equation 2.

$$YLL_i \text{ at age } ad = YLL_i(r, M, \alpha)e^{-rs} \quad 3$$

In Equation 3, s represents the number of discounted years add by subtracting ad with ao .

In order to find the DALYs' value for one patient the YLD and YLL calculated in Equation 1 and 3 respectively are summed up as shown in Equation 4.

$$DALYs_i = YLL_i + YLD_i \quad 4$$

DALYs is measured for each patient and then DALYs of the patients in each arm i.e. AC and HC are summed together as shown in the Equation 5.

$$DALYs = \sum_{i=1}^n DALYs_i \quad 5$$

In Equation 5, the index i shows the patient's number in each arm ranging from 1-171.

To assess the robustness of the effectiveness analysis, the study explores various scenarios by using different combinations of discount rates (r), age weighting modulation factors (M), and age weighing constants in the DALY calculation. This allows for a comprehensive comparison of results and insights into the sensitivity of the effectiveness conclusions. Notably, category 1 adheres to the zero-weighting approach proposed by Murray et al. (2013a).

3.2. Cost measure of health intervention strategies

The social cost i.e. cost incurred by both the National Tuberculosis Program (NTP) of Pakistan and patients and their families during MDR-TB treatment is considered in the research aligned with the WHO's recommendations (2000) on efficient resource allocation. The NTP covers the estimated cost at US\$1,000 per patient for both treatment arms. This includes medical services and food baskets for treatment supporters. However, patients also incurred various direct and indirect costs. Then U.S dollars is considered in historic context averaged as the exchange rate of 104 Pakistani rupee per dollar between 2012-2017. Finally, the cost is taken in the Pakistani rupee for ease of reference in the local context.

3.3. Cost-effectiveness measure of health intervention strategies

Moving further, the cost of saving one year of life adjusted for disability (DALY) is calculated as Cost per DALYs averted. A lower cost per DALY indicates a more cost-effective strategy. Following conventional thresholds, a cost per DALY below the annual GDP per capita is considered highly cost-effective, and below three times the GDP per capita is still considered acceptable, as suggested by Marseille et al. (2015). The Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) derived from Equation 6 is the ratio that compares the incremental cost (difference in cost between ambulatory and hospital arms) to the incremental effectiveness (difference in DALYs averted between the two arms).

Table 1: Patients' Health Outcome

Outcome	Number of Patients
Completed	2
Cured	302
Failed	12
Lost to follow up	46
Not evaluated	8
Still under treatment	6
Died	62

3.4. Participants, design and settings

To calculate the ICER as defined in Equation 6, the secondary data is collected from a randomized control trial (RCT) conducted by the NTP of Pakistan between 2012 and 2017. The RCT enrolled 438 patients diagnosed and registered for MDR-TB treatment. Consenting participants were randomly assigned to either the hospital care (H) or ambulatory care (A) arm, regardless of disease severity. The health outcomes of the patients are shown in Table 1:

The inclusion criteria for the selection of the patients in the study is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Finally, given the availability of data, the study included 342 patients who achieved cure or died. Both treatment arms (AC and HC) adhered to identical medication and follow-up regimens. Examining Table A1 (Appendix), we observe comparable average ages: 32.71 in AC and 33.73 in HC. Statistical analysis found no significant age differences between these groups. Furthermore, applying the Fisher exact test to nominal variables like marital status and gender, and the Wilcoxon rank sum test to ordered categorical variables, revealed no statistically significant differences within the groups. This consistency in other patient characteristics strengthens the study's randomized controlled trial (RCT) design, confirming that selection criteria were not arbitrary. A decision tree model, constructed using Tree Age Pro 2018 (Figure 2), initially analyzed 342 patients equally divided between the AC and HC arms (171 each), following Biau's 2008 approach.

Figure 2: Decision Tree Diagram of MDR-TB Control Strategies

n = total number of patients, p = probability of cure and death, A = ambulatory arm and H = hospital arm

To further investigate the feasibility of widespread implementation, the study then performs CEA to evaluate the economic implications of the intervention strategies.

4. Results and Discussions

In a study of 342 patients with MDR-TB, 81% in the hospital arm and 84% in the ambulatory arm were able to cure, exceeding the WHO target of 75-90% success rate indicating effective treatment implementation in both settings. The Table 2 shows that lower YLL values in the AC compared to the HC across all categories. attributed to lower death rates in AC. This finding suggests effective healthcare interventions and reasonable adherence to treatment protocol in the ambulatory setting that may have been influenced the enhanced medical literacy provided by healthcare professionals to both patients and their families.

Table 2: Years of Life Lost (YLL)

Category	1		2		3		4		5	
r, M, α	0, 0, 0		0.03, 1, 0.04		0.03, 0, 0		0.0596, 1, 0.04		0.0596, 0, 0	
Treatment Arm	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A
Total YLL*	1214.4	996.2	71.1	63.34	20.08	16.54	79.32	67.62	26.71	21.23
YLL per patient	7.10	5.83	0.42	0.37	0.12	0.10	0.46	0.40	0.16	0.12
Standard Error	1.23	0.95	0.17	0.13	0.02	0.02	0.14	0.11	0.03	0.02
Minimum value	0	0	-4.17	-3.47	0	0	-2.89	-2.48	0	0
Maximum value	58.6	50.75	9.38	7.7	0.83	0.72	7.32	6.21	0.96	0.84
C.I. (at 95%)	4.67 to 9.52	3.4 to 8.26	0.08 to 0.75	0.04 to 0.70	0.08 to 0.16	0.06 to 0.14	0.18 to 0.74	0.13 to 0.67	0.11 to 0.21	0.07 to 0.17

r refers to discount rate, M refers to age weighting modulation fraction, α refers to age weighting constant, H and A refers to hospital arm and ambulatory arm respectively, C.I. (at 95%) indicates the upper and lower bounds of the 95% confidence interval surrounding the mean value, providing insights into the range of plausible values with statistical uncertainty, * Total YLL of 171 patients in each arm.

The results of Table 3 show lower total YLD in the HC compared to the AC across all age categories which can be explained by the shorter average duration of disability in the hospital setting (1.14 years) compared to ambulatory care (1.29 years).

Table 3: Years of Life Lived with Disability (YLD)

Category	1		2		3		4		5	
r, M, α	0, 0, 0		0.03, 1, 0.04		0.03, 0, 0		0.0596, 1, 0.04		0.0596, 0, 0	
Treatment Arm	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A
Total YLD*	65.04	72.09	85	99.28	190.6	216.46	86.59	97.06	187.2	211.6
YLL per patient	0.38	0.42	0.50	0.58	1.11	1.27	0.51	0.57	1.09	1.24
Standard Error	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.03
Minimum value	0.03	0.02	-2.86	0.02	0.08	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.08	0.07
Maximum value	0.72	0.71	1.06	1.03	2.1	2.07	1.03	1	2.03	1.99
C.I (at 95%)	0.35 to 0.41	0.39 to 0.45	0.45 to 0.55	0.53 to 0.63	1.03 to 1.19	1.19 to 1.34	0.46 to 0.56	0.52 to 0.62	1.01 to 1.18	1.17 to 1.31

r refers to discount rate, M refers to age weighting modulation fraction, α refers to age weighting constant, , H and A refers to hospital arm and ambulatory arm respectively, C.I. (at 95%)' indicates the upper and lower bounds of the 95% confidence interval surrounding the mean value, providing insights into the range of plausible values with statistical uncertainty.* Total YLD of 171 patients in each arm

Table 4 reveals lower DALYs in AC compared to HC in categories 1 & 4 using the assumptions of no time discounting and zero age weights, resulting from the advantage of having a slightly lower death rate and higher cure rate in AC. However, in categories 2, 3, and 5, higher DALYs are shown for AC. This reversal occurs because the longer average duration of disability in AC outweighs its benefits in terms of lower death rates and higher cure rates (Shabbir 2021).

Table 4: Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs)

Category	1		2		3		4		5	
r, M, α	0,0,0		0.03,1,0.04		0.03,0,0		0.0596,1,0.04		0.0596,0,0	
Treatment Arm	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A
Total DALYs*	1279.45	1069.9	159.44	162.62	210.66	233	165.9	164.68	213.88	232.88
DALYs per patient	7.48	6.26	0.93	0.95	1.23	1.36	0.97	0.96	1.25	1.36
Standard Error	1.22	0.95	0.94	0.13	1.23	0.03	0.14	0.11	0.03	0.03
Minimum value	0.03	0.02	-4.14	-3.26	0.083	0.07	-2.83	-2.3	0.08	0.07
Maximum value	58.63	52.09	9.42	7.95	2.17	2.25	7.36	6.45	2.25	2.29
C.I (at 95%)	5.07 to 9.89	3.85 to 8.67	0.60 to 1.26	0.62 to 1.28	0.16 to 1.30	1.29 to 1.43	0.70 to 1.24	0.69 to 1.23	1.18 to 1.32	1.29 to 1.43

r refers to discount rate, M refers to age weighting modulation fraction, α refers to age weighting constant, , H and A refers to hospital arm and ambulatory arm respectively, C.I. (at 95%)' indicates the upper and lower bounds of the 95% confidence interval surrounding the mean value, providing insights into the range of plausible values with statistical uncertainty.

Examining Table 5, differences in the cost burden associated with AC and HC treatment for MDR-TB can be observed. The AC arm incurs higher overall costs (\$61,606.32) compared to the HC arm (\$52,216.14). The increased cost burden associated with the AC arm can be attributed to the initial treatment phase being delivered in a community setting, resulting in elevated expenses for preventative measures in the household, travel, and potentially higher medical costs compared to hospital-based care.

Table 5: Different Types of Cost Burdens During Treatment of MDR-TB

Type of costs		Cost in PKR		Cost in I\$		Cost in US\$	
		H	A	H	A	H	A
Travelling Cost	All patients	2,209,249	2,432,768	65,771.03	72,425.36	21,242.78	23,392
	Per patient	12,919.58	14,226.71	384.63	423.54	124.23	136.80
	C.I (at 95%)	9,925.3 to 15,913.8	11,761.1to 16,692.3	295.48 to 473.77	350.13 to 496.92	95.4 to 153.0	113.0 to 160.5
Hospitalization Cost	All patients	286,541.8	141,691.6	8,530.57	4,218.27	2,755.20	1,362.41
	Per patient	1675.68	828.61	49.89	24.67	16.11	7.97
	C.I (at 95%)	1,329.2 to 2,022.1	679.6 to 977.5	39.57 to 60.199	20.23 to 29.10	12.78 to 19.44	6.53 to 9.39
Side Effects Treatment Cost	All patients	108,587	162,689.4	3,232.72	4,843.39	1,044.10	1,564.32
	Per patient	635.01	951.40	18.90	28.32	6.11	9.15
	C.I (at 95%)	327.7 to 942.7	490.73 to 1412.0	9.76 to 28.06	14.61 to 42.04	3.15 to 9.06	4.7 to 13.5
Medicine Cost	All patients	234,38.8	46,561.4	697.79	1,386.17	225.4	447.7
	Per patient	137.07	272.29	4.08	8.11	1.32	2.62
	C.I (at 95%)	9.06 to 265.0	47.06 to 591.6	0.27 to 7.89	1.40 to 17.61	0.08 to 2.54	0.45 to 5.68
Lab test Cost	All patients	79,260.48	91,887.8	2,359.65	2,735.57	762.12	883.5365
	Per patient	463.51	537.36	13.80	16.00	4.46	5.17
	C.I (at 95%)	273.3 to 653.6	328.03 to 746.6	8.14 to 19.46	9.76 to 22.23	2.62 to 6.28	3.15 to 7.17
Preventive Measure Cost	All patients	179,834.2	252,994.5	5,353.80	7,531.84	1,729.2	2,432.6
	Per patient	1,051.66	1,479.50	31.31	44.05	10.11	14.23
	C.I (at 95%)	901.4 to 1,201.6	673.5 to 2,285.4	26.84 to 35.78	20.05 to 68.04	8.66 to 12.5	6.4 to 21.9
Patients Relocation Cost	All patients	5,625.3	2,042.5	167.47	60.81	54.089	19.639
	Per patient	32.90	11.94	0.98	0.36	0.32	0.11
	C.I (at 95%)	12.8 to 52.8	16.1 to 40.0	0.38 to 1.52	0.48 to 1.19	0.12 to 0.50	0.15 to 0.38
Room rent	All patients	260,749.2	417,620	7,762.70	12,432.87	2,507.204	4,015.577
	Per patient	1,524.85	2,442.22	45.40	72.71	14.66	23.48
	C.I (at 95%)	234.8 to 2814.8	112.4 to 4771.9	6.99 to 83.79	3.35 to 142.06	2.25 to 27.0	1.08 to 45.8
Home Visits Cost	All patients	43,458.2	91,485	1,293.78	2,723.58	417.867	879.663
	Per patient	254.14	535.00	7.57	15.93	2.44	5.14
	C.I (at 95%)	81.7 to 426.5	251.49 to 818.5	2.43 to 12.69	7.48 to 24.37	0.78 to 4.100	2.41 to 7.87
Fellows Room Rent	All patients	227,990.1	438,528.6	6,787.44	13,055.33	2,192.213	4,216.621
	Per patient	1,333.28	2,564.49	39.69	76.35	12.82	24.66
	C.I (at 95%)	33.27 to 2,633.2	2,503.5 to 6,465.3	58.99 to 78.39	74.53 to 192.47	1.94-30.79	-7.40-39.44
Fellow Transport and Others Cost	All patients	674,362.1	766,854.3	20,076.28	22,829.84	6,484.251	7,373.599
	Per patient	3,943.64	4,484.53	117.41	133.51	37.92	43.12
	C.I (at 95%)	2,363.3 to 5,523.9	3,044.53 to 5,447.8	70.36 to 164.46	90.64 to 162.19	22.7 to 53.1	29.2 to 52.3
Income Loss of Fellows	All patients	285,414.5	351,673.9	8,497.01	10,469.60	2,744.37	3,381.479
	Per patient	1,669.09	2,056.57	49.69	61.23	16.05	19.77
	C.I (at 95%)	1,276 to 2,062.1	1,589.7 to 2,523.4	37.99 to 61.39	47.33 to 75.12	12.69 to 19.8	15.2 to 24.2
Transport Cost of Supporter	All patients	1,045,967	1,210,261	31,139.24	36,030.40	10,057.38	11,637.13
	Per patient	6,116.77	7077.55	182.10	210.70	58.82	68.05
	C.I (at 95%)	5,211.4 to 7,012	6,224.2 to 7,930.8	155.15 to 208.75	185.29 to 236.11	50.1 to 67.4	59.8 to 76.2
Total cost	All patients	5,430,478.21	6,407,057	161,669.5	190,743.0	52,216.14	61,606.32
	Per patient	31,757.2	37,468.2	945.4	1,115.5	305.4	360.3
	C.I (at 95%)	26,305.8 to 37,208.5	32,120.96 to 42,815.37	783.14 to 11.7.75	956.26 to 1274.65	252.9 to 357.7	308.8 to 411.6

H denotes the hospital arm and A represents the ambulatory care arm. Costs are presented in Pakistani Rupee (PKR), International Dollar (I\$), and US Dollar (USD). C.I. (at 95%) indicates the upper and lower bounds of the 95% confidence interval surrounding the mean value, providing insights into the range of plausible values with statistical uncertainty.

Table 6 presents the cost per DALY averted for both HC and AC, shedding light on the cost effectiveness of each treatment option in terms of saving an additional year of healthy life. A cost-effective strategy should require spending less than the average annual income per person to save a life-year. However, spending below three times GDP per capita can still be considered as cost-effective.

Table 6: Cost per DALYs Averted in treatment arms i.e. Hospital vs. Ambulatory care

Category	1		2		3		4		5	
r, M, α	0,0,0		0.03,1,0.04		0.03,0,0		0.0596,1,0.04		0.0596,0,0	
Treatment Arm	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A
PKR	4,244.4	5,988	34,059.7	39,398.9	25,778.4	27,498.1	32,731.5	38,906.1	25,390.3	27,512.3
I\$	126.4	178.3	1,014	1172.9	767.4	818.6	974.4	1158.3	755.9	819.1
US \$	40.8	57.6	327.5	378.8	247.9	264.4	314.7	374.1	244.1	264.5

r refers to discount rate, M refers to age weighting modulation fraction, α refers to age weighting constant, H and A refers to hospital arm and ambulatory arm respectively, and Costs are shown in Pakistani Rupee (PKR), International Dollar (I\$), and US Dollar (US\$)

Finally, the Table 7 presents the ICER values calculated using Equation 6. The ICER reflects the additional cost required per unit of health outcome gained (one DALY saved) when comparing AC to HC. Analyzing ICER helps identify the dominant strategy in cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA). The Category 1 and 4 show that AC has lower DALYs (more effective) but incurs a higher cost (PKR 976,579, equivalent to US\$9,390.18), resulting in a higher ICER. This implies that AC provides greater health benefits but at a larger cost per additional DALY saved compared to hospital care.

Table 7: Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio

Category	1	2	3	4	5
r, M, α	0,0,0	0.03,1,0.04	0.03,0,0	0.0596,1,0.04	0.0596,0,0
ICER in PKR	-	8,875.	1,26	-	2,950.
ICER in I\$	4,491.69	75	3.42	45,437.2	27
ICER US \$	133.72	264.24	1	1,352.70	87.83
Result	-43.19	85.34	12.1	-437	28.37
	The ambulatory arm is cost-effective	The ambulatory care is more costly and less effective	The ambulatory care is more costly and less effective	The ambulatory arm is cost-effective	The ambulatory care is more costly and less effective

Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) values are presented in the currency of the intervention they represent, allowing for direct comparison. PKR for Pakistani Rupee, I\$ for the international dollar, and US\$ for the United States Dollar., Additionally, benchmark comparisons for each intervention utilize the corresponding GDP per capita in the same currency.

The ICER analysis in Table 7 suggests no continuous dominant strategy across all categories. To assess the robustness of these findings, a one-way sensitivity analysis was conducted by varying the cost of both HC and AC. The descriptive statistics and t-test results for comparing DALYs and HC and AC are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Group Means and Significance Testing

Category	1		2		3		4		5		Cost of H and A	
r, M, α	0,0,0		0.03,1,0.04		0.03,0,0		0.0596,1,0.04		0.0596,0,0			
Treatment Arm	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A	H	A
Mean	7.48	6.26	0.95	0.94	1.24	1.36	1.25	1.36	0.97	0.96	31080.3	36553.5
The t value	0.75		0.02		-2.43***		-2.3***		0.04		-1.42	

r refers to discount rate, M refers to age weighting modulation fraction, α refers to age weighting constant, H and A refers to hospital arm and ambulatory arm respectively, and Costs are shown in Pakistani Rupee (PKR), International Dollar (I\$), and US Dollar (US\$), *** refers to significant at 1% level of significance & SD mean standard deviation

The t-test reveals statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$) in DALYs between the two arms only for categories 3 and 4. This indicates that in these categories, the average DALYs for hospital care differ significantly from those for ambulatory care. For the remaining categories (1, 2, and 5), as well as for the cost data, the t-test fails to reject the null hypothesis (Shabbir et al 2015 and Mughal et al 2023). This means that again, we cannot statistically conclude a difference between the average DALYs or costs for HC and AC in these categories showing the both arms have a potential to play a role in effective treatment.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study employs cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) to evaluate two MDR-TB treatment arms in Pakistan namely HC and AC with the primary goal to estimate the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of both arms to identify the more cost-effective treatment option in Pakistan. We have analyzed the data from 342 MDR-TB patients registered at the NTP of Pakistan between 2012-2017 and DALYs averted and associated social costs are calculated. Overall treatment success rate came out to be 82.5% with higher cure rates and lower death rates in ambulatory care. Hospital care exhibits lower cost per DALY, suggesting potential cost savings but both arms have cost per DALY averted below GDP per capita per year, indicating cost-effectiveness for Pakistan. Moreover, no consistent dominance in ICER analysis by either arm indicating both arms possess strengths under specific assumptions, allowing for complementary use.

Based on the results of the study, some important policy recommendation can be drawn. The AC minimizes the hospital waiting lists and facilitates home-based treatment hence should be focused by the health care providers aligned with WHO recommendations. Hospital-initiated treatment, with expert supervision, can shorten disability duration and reduce patient costs but poses challenges for hospital capacity and cure rates. Hence,

ambulatory care, despite higher costs, plays a crucial role in reducing disease burden through lower death rates and higher cure rates.

6. References

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